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Annotation: In this article, the life experiences and creativity of Maksud Sheikhzadeh, our nation's favorite poet, dramatist, literary scientist, translator, pedagogue, are widely interpreted. At the same time, the article arouses great interest in the life and work of Maksud Sheikhzadeh and encourages him to study it thoroughly.

Key words: Maksud Sheikhzadeh, poem, drama, epic, Ten poems, Consonants, Tashkentnama epic.

Аннотация: В данной статье широко осмыслены жизненный опыт и творчество любимца нашего народа поэта, драматурга, литературоведа, переводчика, педагога Максуда Шейхзаде. В то же время статья вызывает большой интерес к жизни и творчеству Максуда Шейхзаде и побуждает его досконально изучить ее.

Ключевые слова: Максуда Шейхзаде, поэма, драма, эпос, Десять стихотворений, Согласные, эпос Ташкентнама.

Maksud Maqsumbek's son Sheikhzada (Maksud Sheikhzada) was born on November 7, 1908 in the city of Aktash, Ganja region, Republic of Azerbaijan. Maksud Sheikhzadeh is a poet, dramatist, literary critic, translator, pedagogue. Honored Artist of Uzbekistan (1964). Graduated from medical school in Baku (1925). At first, he worked as a teacher at the 1st level Azerbaijani school in Darband, at the Technical College of Education and Training in Boynaq. In 1927, he was arrested as a member of a counter-revolutionary organization, and in February 1928 he was exiled to Tashkent. After studying for a short time at the Oriental Faculty of the University of Central Asia (1928), Shaykhzoda served in the editorial offices of "Sharq Haqiqiti" (1929-1932), "Kyzil Uzbekiston", "Yosh Leninchi" newspapers (1932), "Guliston" magazine (1933-1934). In 1933, he passed the exam for all courses of the Pedagogical Institute in Baku and entered the post-graduate course under the Science Committee (1934). At the same time, he worked as a researcher at the Institute of Language and Literature (1935-1938). From 1938 until the end of his life, he lectured on the history of Uzbek literature, first in the evening, then in the daytime, in pedagogical institutes.

In the tragedy "Jalaluddin Manguberdi" (1944), written during the Second World War, Sheikhzade described the fighting courage of the last branch of Khorezm who fought for the freedom and independence of their country against the Mongol invaders. In the tragedy "Mirzo Ulugbek" (1961), Sheikhzada portrayed

the main character of Amir Temur and the renaissance of the Uzbek people during the Timurid period. By describing the last 2 years of Sheikhzada Ulugbek's life in this work, written in Shakespearean style, it has been truthfully shown that he was a famous scientist, a just and truthful statesman, who took a worthy place in the history of world science, and at the same time, he was a weak person in front of the bigoted forces of the kingdom. The release of the tragedy "Mirzo Ulugbek", written with Shakespearean scale and warmth, was a great event in the history of Uzbek dramaturgy and theater. The film "The Star of Ulugbek" (1964) created by the director L. Fayziyev based on the script of Sheikhzada allowed the general public to get to know the great Uzbek scientist and his tragic fate. Translation played an important role in the expansion of Shaikhzada's range of literary knowledge and the enrichment of his work with the artistic experience of classical world writers.

He Sh. Rustaveli's epic "Pakhlan covered with a tiger skin" (in collaboration), sonnets of U. Shakespeare, A.S. Pushkin's poems, the epic "The Copper Rider", the tragedy "Mozart and Salieri", M.Yu. He skillfully translated Lermontov's poems and the epic "Prisoner of the Caucasus", as well as some works of Nizami, Fuzuli, Mirza Fatali Akhundov, Aesop, Aeschylus, Goethe, Byron, Mayakovsky, Nazim Hikmat and other writers into Uzbek. The poet died in 1967 in Tashkent. In 2001, he was awarded the Order "For Great Services" for his great contribution to the development of Uzbek literature and culture. Maksud Sheikhzadeh's contribution to the development of Uzbek literature and culture was duly honored by independent Uzbekistan and its government. A number of schools and streets are named after him.

Maksud Sheikhzade has a great place in the development of Uzbek poetry of the 20th century. Colorful form and content, upbeat spirit, vivid images in Oktam's poems filled with pathos, symbolism, sonority in words, musical skill give a unique artistic integrity to the poet's works, similar emotions fill the heart of the reader. wakes up the wave. The poet never looked for bookish, artificial problems. First of all, he addresses the issues that excite him and open the eyes of his civil and poetic cells. The emotions evoked by the poet move to the heart and consciousness of the reader. He starts his new life. His poems are full of beautiful artistic images. To the poet, sometimes a boat seems like a dot in the sea, a "spot on the water", and sometimes the tail of a baby sounds like a "question to the horizon". Sheikhzada's poems were published in dozens of collections such as "For a quarter of a century", "Dunyo baqi", "Alley". These poems were sung with the dreams, love, pains and hopes of contemporary

people living with high human dreams. It is true that in his forty-year career, Sheikhzada also sang about Lenin, the Kremlin, Soviets, races and sects. But this is the stamp of the poet's fate and work of the time and system. However, the value of Sheikhzada's poetry is determined not by the works of this direction, but by the works that serve to enrich the reader with such beautiful moments by elegantly and optimistically reflecting the delicate and unique situations of the human heart.

Sheikhzada considered the main task of the poet to be "to educate the human spirit, to increase the elements of goodness in a person, to raise the sense of beauty and sophistication to a higher level in the people." It is correct to proceed from this point of view in relation to his lyrical philosophical epic "Tashkentnoma". These thoughts of Shoi can be the starting point for most of his poems. According to Maksud Sheikhzadeh, poetry is one of the greatest blessings in life, and poetry is one of the incomparable beauties. In his poem "Poetry is the sister of true beauty", Shaikhzada sings about the essence of poetry, which shines throughout his work, which gives a person infinite beauty, spiritual redemption and evolution, and strives to open new aspects of it. . The idea in the title of the poem, in one sense, does not seem to be new. Similar views can be found in the works of Navoi, Pushkin, Yesenin, Cholpon. However, according to the unwritten rules of poetry, the main issue is not only the thought and meaning that motivates the work, but also the way of their artistic manifestation, the ability to awaken new wave emotions in the psyche of the reader. is a horse. Sheikhzada's work "Poetry is the sister of real beauty" is valuable in these aspects.

In the work, poetry is glorified as one of the great qualities that keep human nature and life alive. Acquaintance with poetry, according to the author, enriches a person's character, strength, and spirituality, and has a strong influence on the perfection of his spirit. Poets and writers described Maksud Sheikhzade as follows: Sheikhzade was different from all of us not only in the sense of intellect, but also in the sense of appearance. Mukhtar Agha's innocent question did not seem to reach him. On the contrary, in all places, at all times, in all environments and conditions, he exuded a sense of pride that enriched his heart. He smiled and even proudly said that he was from Azerbaijan, that he came from Azerbaijan. When he said these words, Maksud's face looked like the sun had moved from the sky (from the page of memories about Maksud Sheikhzadeh).

Maksud Shaykhzada, who created in the ranks of great artists of Uzbek literature - Gafur Ghulam and Oybek, was a poet bursting with poetry. His works embody

great revolutionary ideals, passionate patriotic feelings, and the bright echo of a burning heart that lived with truly creative emotions (Mirzo Ibrohimov, People's Writer of Azerbaijan "Forty years ago, one of the great figures of Uzbek literature of the 20th century, Maksud Shaikhzada's heart stopped beating as a victim. During the past period, most of his peers, followers, students and admirers have passed away, and the generation that was born and grew up during this period does not hear his passionate words, does not see his radiant face, but enjoys the generosity of his soul. As a result, it is difficult for them to perceive Sheikhzadeh not only as a great poet, but also as a great person, and to bow before his brilliant talent. That is why the life and work of this fiery poet is a unique figure. It is the task of us, contemporaries, to write about it," writes Naim Karimov.

Maksud Shaykhzade is a poet, dramatist, literary critic, translator, pedagogue who made a great contribution to the development of Uzbek literature, suffered during the authoritarian regime. In his poems, feelings such as enthusiasm, love, and love for the motherland can be felt. The life and work of Maksud Sheikhzade awakens love and warmth in the human heart. Studying the life, creativity and heritage of our ancestors, being aware of them and applying them to life - only and only leads us to success. In Maksud Sheikhzadeh, the way of life forms a strong character in us. His ability to endure life's blows with patience and his creativity without stopping from his work can be an example for all of us.

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